

Development of a Patient Education Program: Non-Pharmacological Interventions for Management of Chronic Low Back Pain

Millicent Muthike, DNP, RN; Manal Alatrash, PhD, RN; Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC

Background

- 80% of adults suffer from chronic low back pain (CLBP)
- 3% to 4% CLBP sufferers take opioids
- Cost: \$100 Billion for CLBP
- In 2016 Opioid crisis declared
- CDC guidelines

Statement of Problem

- Decreased opioid medications
- Non-pharmacological Interventions (NPIs) not offered
- Pain undertreated

Statement of Purpose

- Design, implement & evaluate an educational program by assessing changes in knowledge, attitudes & beliefs related to NPIs
- Develop an educational protocol with evidence-based practices (EBP) & the 2016 CDC's updated guidelines

Methods

- Quality Improvement Project with interventional pretest-posttest design
- Private clinic in San Bernardino County
- 30 Adults with CLBP on opioids
- Pretest surveys & education
- Pamphlet, pain tool
- Twice a week contact & post surveys

Health Promotion Model

Results & Analysis

- Knowledge increased ($p < .001$), NPIs increased

- Pain level decreased ($p = .049$)

- Pain interfered less with their general activities & enjoyment of life ($p = .024; .017$)

- Attitudes and opiates: no significant change

Demographics	n	%
Age		
25-34	5	16.67
35-44	6	20
45-54	9	30
55-64	9	30
≥75	1	3.33
Marital status		
Single	15	50
Married	11	36.67
Widowed	1	3.33
Divorced	3	10
Gender		
Males	6	20
Females	24	80
Annual Income		
\$0-\$9,999	12	40.00
\$10,000-\$24,999	11	36.67
\$25,000-\$49,999	3	10.00
\$50,000-\$74,999	1	3.33
Prefer not to answer	3	10

Discussion

- Demographics represented clinic population
- Increased Knowledge
- Understanding pain
- Reduced skepticism
- Increase in NPIs
 - Self-administered
 - Convenient
 - Non-invasive, non-threatening
 - Pain relief
 - Increased contact

Strengths & Limitations

- Design interventional, addressed project purposes
- Monitor progress
- No Attrition
- Patient provider communication
- Positive results
- Lack of generalizability
- Pretest posttest effect
- Self-reported data, time

Future Implications

- NPIs: First method of intervention
- Patient-provider communication
- Educational programs integration to routine care for pain
- Develop an educational protocol that follows EBP and the CDC's guidelines & recommendations.